

Lingbao Canon: Perfect Script in Five Tablets 五篇真文 and Jade Instruction Written in Red 赤書玉訣

By Liying Xu, Arizona State University

Entry tags: Religious Group, Literary Chinese, Text, Lingbao (Numinous Treasure), Language, Daoism, Daoist text, Classical-Middle-Modern Sinitic, Sino-Tibetan, Sinitic, Lingbao (Numinous Treasure or Sacred Jewel) text

The Lingbao (Numinous Treasure) scriptures arose around the early fifth century CE, immediately after the prevalence of the Shangqing (Upper Clarity) scriptures. We are able to get a general picture of the early Lingbao scriptures because of the work of Lu Xiuqing 陸修靜 (406-477) who collected and promulgated the scriptures. The catalogue of early Lingbao scriptures written by Lu Xiuqing is the earliest reliable source for modern scholars to get a glimpse of the landscape of the Lingbao movement. However, Lu's original catalogue was lost, and the restored copy based on a discovered Tang copy of Dunhuang manuscripts caused many academic issues. Basically, Lu Xiuqing's catalogue divided the Lingbao canon into two sections: the Old Lingbao scriptures (jiu jing 舊經) instructed by the Heavenly Worthy of Primordial Commencement (Yuanshi Tianzun 元始天尊) and the newly revealed scriptures (xin jing 新經) instructed by Xu Laile, the Perfected of Most Utmost (Taiji Zhenren Xu Laile 太極真人徐來勒). The Old Lingbao scriptures start with two essential scriptures: the first one is Scripture of Celestial Writing, Perfect Script in Jade (or Five) Tablets, Written in Red by Five Elders of Primordial Commencement 元始五老赤書玉 (五) 篇真文天書經 that introduce the emergence of celestial scripts; the second one is Wondrous Scripture of Jade Instruction Written in Red by Numinous Treasure, Cavern Mystery of Most High 太上洞玄靈寶赤書玉訣妙經 that is read as commentary for the celestial scripts. Therefore, these two scriptures which are preserved in the in the Daoist Canon of Zhengtong (Zhengtong daoang 正統道藏) of the Ming are closely related to each other. The first scripture demonstrates the Daoist concept of genesis and celestial provenance starting from the emergence of the Perfect Scripts which symbolizes the openness of the new Kalpa cycle. The Perfected Scripts were regarded as the supreme and most powerful force in the Daoist cosmogeny, but they were invisible and intangible to humans. Then the Perfected Scripts were materialized by the highest deity Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement (Yuanshi Tianzun 元始天尊). Then he transmitted them to other celestial beings. The materialized Perfected Scripts were still unintelligible to humans. So, the celestial beings took the responsibility to translate the Perfected Scripts into the form of the human language which are in total thirty-six juan scriptures and two juan oral instructions. These scriptures were called Old Lingbao Scriptures that were categorized into ten sections. The scripture contains the images of Cloudy seals of the Perfect Script and the Five Directional Talismans, followed by the instructions for use of the talismans. The second scripture Jade Instructions is regarded, to some degree, as the commentary of the first one. It introduces how the Lingbao scriptures, which are translation and interpretation of the Perfected Scripts done by the Most High Lord of Great Dao 太上大道君 (abbr. the Lord Dao 道君 or the Dao 道) and other celestial beings, were transmitted to the human world at the end of the Five Kalpa Cycles. The two humans who received the Lingbao scriptures from the Lord Dao were Wang Longci 王龍賜 and A Qiuzeng 阿丘曾. This scripture also provides the methods and rituals on how to use the Instruction of Five Directions to eliminate crimes and disasters. Scholars have noticed a great number of terms and concepts in the Lingbao scriptures that were adapted from Buddhist scriptures. However, the meanings and the connotations of these terms were changed and became distinct from those in the Buddhist context in order to serve the Daoist purposes, or to solve the newly emerged challenges that Daoist were encountering.

Date Range: 500 CE - 1000 CE

Region: Jiangnan Region

Region tags: China, Yangzi River Valley

The normally classified Jiangnan Area.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Zhengtong Daoist Canon of the Ming 正統道藏

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5a0022/>

– Source 1 Description: 元始五老赤書玉篇真文天書經 (正統道藏)

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5b0036/>

– Source 2 Description: 太上洞玄靈寶赤書玉訣妙經 (正統道藏)

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5a0022/>

– Source 1 Description: 元始五老赤書玉篇真文天書經 (正統道藏)

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.kanripo.org/text/KR5b0036/>

– Source 2 Description: 太上洞玄靈寶赤書玉訣妙經 (正統道藏)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=en&res=582667>

– Source 1 Description: 元始五老赤書玉篇真文天書經 (正統道藏)

– Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/wiki.pl?if=en&res=987941>

– Source 2 Description: 太上洞玄靈寶赤書玉訣妙經 (正統道藏)

– Source 1 URL: <https://taolibrary.com/category/category109/c1090169.htm?pageno=1>

– Source 1 Description: 元始五老赤書玉篇真文天書經 (中華道藏)

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.taolibrary.com/category/category109/c1090170.htm?pageno=26>

– Source 2 Description: 太上洞玄靈寶赤書玉訣妙經 (中華道藏)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

- ↳ Inked
 - with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

- ↳ Specify type of paper
 - Specify: Block-printing

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: unclear

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: the version preserved in the Daoist Canon has been modified before.

Notes: The version preserved in the Daoist Canon of Ming has been modified because some terms and passages are different from the quotations from other Daoist collections according to scholars' studies.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

- ↳ Tomb
 - No

- ↳ Cemetery
 - No

- ↳ Temple
 - Yes

Notes: The earliest printing version of the Zhengtong Daoist Canon of the Ming was stored in a

Daoist temple "White Cloud Temple" in Beijing 北京白雲觀.

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– No

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

↳ Monument
– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point
– No

↳ Cave(s)
– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The Daoist Canon of Ming was original stored in the imperial library and some Daoist temples. However, most of them were destroyed due to war or fire. The only version survived version was the one stored in White Cloud Temple in Beijing.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography or imagery present?

Select all that apply

– Religious space with restricted access

↳ Are there distinct or notable features or attributes in the religious group's iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Compared with other Daoist traditions, these texts development a broad and complete cosmological cycle and new lineage of transmission which can be characterized as a reform.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: Those who hear Lingbao scriptures can be saved and delivered to the next world.

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: The Perfected Scriptures in Five Tablets have fourteen "Virtues" (de 德), and they can bestow fourteen "Blessings" (fu 福) to readers. The readers can also benefit from twelve "Minds" (nian 念) when they read these texts. Furthermore, readers will receive twelve "Reward" (bao 報), twelve "Graces" (en 恩), and fourteen "Achievements" (gong 功) from these texts.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: They will be saved and delivered to the next world.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The nature of the ritual practice is to communicate with celestial beings, especially the Five Lords who are in charge of the Perfected Scripts in the Five Directions, so that they can remove their crimes, save their ancestors, and eliminate disasters.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– No

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: The rituals take place on Eight Node Days (bajie 八節) or the dates match the practitioners' birthdays calculated by the ten Heavenly Stems (tiangan 天干) and twelve Earthly Branches (dizhi 地支).

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: During rituals, Daoists will consume talismans written in different color of ink on

different colors of paper or silk. They also need to ingest Five Sprouts (wuya 五芽), the name for the essence of qi in five directions.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures contains 688 Perfected Scripts which are cloudy seal scripts in shape.

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– Yes

Notes: These Perfected Scripts can save people from the calamitous flood at the end of this kalpa cycle.

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Yes

↳ Promotes knowledge?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Yes

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– Yes

↳ Physical healing

– Yes

↳ Mental/psychological healing

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– Yes

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– Yes

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– Yes

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: Sometimes, the talismans with the Perfected Scripts need to be burned to transform to the mist after incantation.

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The color, materials (silk), and size are various to match the different directions, dates (Heavenly Stem and Early Branches), and practitioners' birthdays.

↳ Specify

– Specify: The color, materials (silk), and size are various to match the different directions, dates (Heavenly Stem and Early Branches), and practitioners' birthdays.

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

↳ Calligraphy?

– Yes

Notes: These scriptures contains 688 Cloudy Seal Scripts in talismans.

↳ Illustrations?

– No

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The authority was established through narrative of cosmology, transmission lineage, and the authority of the compiler.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

↳ How are the volumes ordered?

– Specify: These two scriptures are on the top of Lu Xiuqing's catalogue which contains thirty-six scrolls divided into ten sections.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Macro-temporal? (Related to really large sections of time; kalpas in Hinduism, for example)

Notes: It is related to Daoist Kalpa cycle.

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– No

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– No

↳ Pilgramages?

– No

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: It is the Ghost Mansion 鬼府 of Fengdu 酆都 in the north where all the dead and ghosts are investigated.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– No

Notes: It is Transcendent (xian 仙) form

↳ In animal/plant form?

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– Yes

Notes: Adherents will become Transcendent by Wheeling Cycle (zhuanglun chengxian 轉輪成仙), which means rebirth.

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: The supreme high god in the Lingbao scripture is Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement (yuanshi tianzun) 元始天尊 who refined the Perfected Script and made them materialized.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
 - ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - No
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: The supreme power in the Lingbao scriptures is Perfected Scripts rather than the supreme high god Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement (yuanshi tianzun 元始天尊). The high god Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement is in charge of

refining the Perfected Scripts and decide if it is the perfected time to transmit celestial writings to humans.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– No

Notes: The supreme high god Celestial Worthy of Primordial Commencement (yuanshi tianzun 元始天尊) only communicates with celestial beings and order the celestial beings to transmit Lingbao scriptures to human beings.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The non-human supernatural beings, such as Golden Dragon, Phoenix, White Tiger, and divine birds will present when the Daoist practitioners are actualizing spirits during the rituals.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: Most of those supernatural animals appear at the auspicious signs.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Human beings can become Transcendent (xian 仙) or Perfected (zhenren 真人) after receiving the Lingbao scriptures and practicing accordingly.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?
– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?
– Field doesn't know

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: There is a Demon King (mo wang 魔王) who present as the antagonist to test those Daoist practitioners.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– Yes

↳ Libations?
– Yes

↳ Food?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– Yes

↳ Daily life objects?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: gold, jade, and silk.

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– No

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Yes

Notes: They care about Kalpa Cycles. The Perfected Scripts can not to be transmitted to humans until the end of the fifth Kalpa cycles.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Specify: They care about if the Daoist practitioners could keep precepts, practice retreat, follow the teaching of Lingbao scriptures, and perform the rituals on the specific dates.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - No
 - Notes: The punishment can be done by different deities according to the transgressions they have committed.
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
 - ↳ Done by other entities or through other means
 - Yes
 - Notes: Humans merits and transgressions are recorded by Three Officials. The Three Officials then report to the high deities. The deity Three Corpses (sanshi 三尸) is also in charge of recording humans merits and transgressions. People will be send to either heavenly realm or the otherworld to be interrogated or punished based on these reports.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: Sometime the punishment is done because the celestial writings are leaked carefully to the wrong person.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: The punishment will reach to their living and dead parents.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done only by high god
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - Yes

↳ Other?

– Yes

Notes: The rewards can be bestowed in the afterlife due to their descendent' merits.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– Yes

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

– Specify: These scriptures list many rewards including Twelve Rewards (bao 報), Twelve Graces (en 恩), and Fourteen Achievement (gong 功)。

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– Yes

Notes: The eschatology is related to the special concept "Yang Nine and Hundred Six" (yangjiu bailiu 陽九百六) which is related to a theory of calculation about the flood and calamity in the Han period.

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: According to the calculation of "Yang Nine and Hundred Six" (yangjiu bailiu 陽九百六), the flood and drought will appear cyclically. But the calculation is very complicated and unreliable.

- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - Yes
 - Notes: They need to read the Lingbao scriptures and practice accordingly.
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - No
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - Yes
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: The cyclical eschatology is called kalpa (jie 劫) which is divided into great kalpa and less kalpa in the Lingbao scriptures.
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - Yes
 - ↳ All religious in-group members will survive
 - No
 - ↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive
 - Yes
 - ↳ All members of the sample region will survive
 - No
 - ↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton
 - No

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: Only those selected as Seed People (zhongren 種人) or those recite and practice Lingbao scriptures will be survived.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: There are Fourteen Virtues (de 德) used to describe the nature of Perfected Scripts.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Monogamy (males)

– Field doesn't know

Monogamy (females)

– Field doesn't know

Other sexual constraints (males)

– Field doesn't know

Other sexual constraints (females)

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require castration?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A nation-state

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Yes

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Yes

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: The disciples who received Lingbao scriptures from masters will have great blessings and be saved during the calamity.

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Lingbao Canon: Perfect Script in Five Tablets 五篇真文 and Jade Instruction Written in Red 赤書玉訣, Bokenkamp, Stephen. "The Early Lingbao Scriptures and the Origins of Daoist Monasticism". *Cahiers D'extrême-asie* 20 (2011): 95-124.

Reference: Lingbao Canon: Perfect Script in Five Tablets 五篇真文 and Jade Instruction Written in Red 赤書玉訣, Ōfuchi Ninji 大淵忍爾. "on Ku Ling-pao-ching.". *Acta Asiatica* 27 (1974): 33-56.

Reference: Lingbao Canon: Perfect Script in Five Tablets 五篇真文 and Jade Instruction Written in Red 赤書玉訣, Bokenkamp, Stephen. "'death and Ascent in Ling - Pao Taoism.". *Taoist Resources* 1, no. 2 (1989): 1-17.

Reference: Lingbao Canon: Perfect Script in Five Tablets 五篇真文 and Jade Instruction Written in Red 赤書玉訣, Lü Pongzhi. "'the Jade Instructions on the Red Writings for Summoning Ghosts and Demons of the Northern Feng Mountain and the Five Lingbao True Writs.". In *Exorcism in Daoism-a Berlin Symposium*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, , 2011.

